

Exploring the Orality of the Liat Pullagajjat Tradition: Strengthening the Character of Generation 5.0 in Matotonan Village, South Siberut

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Abstract

This article discusses the orality of the “liat pullagajjat” tradition which is a ritual tradition in Matotonan Village, South Siberut, Mentawai Islands Regency, West Sumatra Province, Indonesia. This oral tradition not only functions as a ritual tradition for the community but also as a village cleansing tradition by summoning ancestral spirits. This research method is a qualitative research method with an oral tradition, ethnography, History and Anthropology approach. The data collection techniques used are observation, interviews, and documentation in the form of recording the liat pullagajjat ritual. The author's data analysis technique is carried out by reducing data, presenting data, and verifying. The results of this study are the liat pullagajjat tradition as an educational medium that conveys important character values for the younger generation. In the context of Generation 5.0 which is marked by the use of digital technology, this article highlights the importance of preserving and integrating oral traditions in modern education. By utilizing digital platforms, the younger generation can more easily access, understand, and apply these values in everyday life, so that adaptive, ethical, and responsible individuals are created. The ritual process in the implementation of the Liat Pullagajjat tradition begins with Lia Siboitok (taddat lia), Sikebbukat sibakkat katcaila, Pasibitbit Sipitto', Lia Sikarua, Iriq toitet Iriq toitet, Lajot Simagre, Lia Sikatelu, Uraji sainak, and Pukalaibok. This ritual is guided by all sikerei in the villages of Matotonan, Madobag and Butni which are located in the South Siberut sub-district of the Mentawai Islands Regency. The Liat Pullagajjat tradition as a cultural heritage of the ancestors of the Mentawai people is a reflection of the extinct Arat Sabulungan. This research can contribute to the development of character education in the digital era and strengthen local cultural identity amidst globalization.

Keywords: orality, liat pullagajjat, character values, generation 5.0, matotonan village, culture.

Abstrak

Artikel ini membahas tentang kelisanan tradisi “liat pullagajjat” yang merupakan tradisi ritual di Desa Matotonan, Siberut Selatan, Kabupaten Kepulauan Mentawai, Provinsi Sumatera Barat, Indonesia. Tradisi lisan ini tidak hanya berfungsi sebagai tradisi ritual bagi masyarakat tetapi juga sebagai tradisi pembersihan desa dengan memanggil roh leluhur. Metode penelitian ini adalah metode penelitian kualitatif dengan pendekatan tradisi lisan, etnografi, Sejarah dan Antropologi. Teknik pengumpulan data yang digunakan adalah observasi, wawancara, dan dokumentasi berupa pencatatan ritual liat pullagajjat. Teknik analisis data penulis dilakukan dengan cara mereduksi data, menyajikan data, dan memverifikasi. Hasil penelitian ini adalah tradisi liat pullagajjat sebagai media pendidikan yang menyampaikan nilai-nilai karakter yang penting bagi generasi muda. Dalam konteks Generasi 5.0 yang ditandai dengan pemanfaatan teknologi digital, artikel ini menyoroti pentingnya melestarikan dan mengintegrasikan tradisi lisan dalam pendidikan modern. Dengan memanfaatkan platform digital, generasi muda dapat lebih mudah mengakses, memahami, dan menerapkan nilai-nilai tersebut dalam kehidupan sehari-hari, sehingga terciptalah pribadi yang adaptif, beretika, dan bertanggung jawab. Adapun proses ritual dalam pelaksanaan tradisi Liat Pullagajjat dimulai dari Lia Siboitok (taddat lia), Sikebbukat sibakkat katcaila, Pasibitbit Sipitto', Lia Sikarua, Iriq toitet Iriq toitet, Lajot Simagre, Lia Sikatelu, Uraji sainak, dan Pukalaibok ritual ini dipandu oleh semua sikerei yang ada di desa Matotonan, Madobag dan Butni yang berada di kecamatan Siberut Selatan kabupaten Kepulauan Mentawai. tradisi Liat Pullagajjat sebagai warisan budaya leluhur dari masyarakat Mentawai yang merupakan cerminan Arat Sabulungan yang telah punah. Penelitian ini dapat memberikan kontribusi bagi pengembangan pendidikan karakter di era digital dan memperkuat identitas budaya lokal di tengah globalisasi.

Kata kunci: kelisanan, liat pullagajjat, nilai-nilai karakter, generasi 5.0, desa matotonan, budaya

INTRODUCTION

Oral tradition is an important part of cultural heritage that not only stores historical values, but also functions as a tool to shape the character of the younger generation. In Matotonan Village, South Siberut, there is an oral tradition known as Liat Pullagajjat, which has great potential in strengthening the character of generation 5.0. This article aims to explore how this tradition can contribute to the formation of character and identity of the younger generation in the digital era.

Oral tradition is one of the rich and valuable cultural heritages, which not only stores historical values, but also functions as a means of education and character formation. In Matotonan Village, South Siberut, there is an oral tradition known as Liat Pullagajjat. This tradition is not only part of the cultural identity of the local community, but also has great potential in strengthening the character of the younger generation in the 5.0 era, which is marked by technological advances and rapid social change.

Generation 5.0 refers to a generation that is able to adapt to advanced technology while maintaining humanitarian and cultural values. In this context, Liat Pullagajjat plays an important role in teaching values such as cooperation, respect, and responsibility to the younger generation. Through the stories, songs, and

performances contained in this tradition, children and adolescents in Matotonan Village are invited to understand and appreciate their cultural heritage, while preparing themselves to face challenges in an increasingly complex world.

This article aims to explore how the orality of the Liat Pullagajjat tradition can contribute to strengthening the character of generation 5.0 in Matotonan Village. By understanding the role and meaning of this tradition, it is hoped that the community can appreciate and preserve it more as part of an effort to build a generation that is not only technologically intelligent, but also rich in cultural and moral values.

RESEARCH METHOD

This research was conducted using a qualitative method with an ethnographic, oral tradition, history, and anthropological approach, using a case study method. Data were collected through interviews, participant observation, and document analysis. Interviews were conducted with 15 informants, including traditional leaders, teachers, and local youth. Observations were conducted during activities involving Liat Pullagajjat, such as performances and training by recording during the Liat Pullagajjat ritual.

This research uses a qualitative approach with a case study method. Data were collected through:

1. Interviews: Researchers conducted in-depth interviews with 15 informants, including traditional leaders, teachers, and local youth, to understand the meaning and role of Liat Pullagajjat in everyday life.
2. Participatory Observation: Researchers were involved in community activities related to Liat Pullagajjat, such as performances and training, to observe interactions and their impact on participants.
3. Document Analysis: Researchers analyzed related documents, including historical records and educational materials related to Liat Pullagajjat.

The data obtained were analyzed thematically to identify patterns and themes that emerged from interviews and observations.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Matotonan Village is located on the island of South Siberut with a population of almost 80 percent Muslim. Matotonan Village is a village located in the District of South Siberut, Mentawai Islands Regency, West Sumatra Province, Indonesia. Based on the latest data, the population of Matotonan Village is around 1,410 people. Matotonan Village has 5 hamlets, namely (Ma Tek Tek, Ma Bek Bek, Marui Baga, Knikdog and Onga hamlet). The people in Matotonan Village adhere to two main religions, namely Islam and Catholicism. Around 84% of the population is Muslim, while 16% are Catholic. The majority of the population works as farmers and ranchers, each around 25% of the total population. This reflects the agrarian tradition that has existed since their ancestors. Matotonan Village can be accessed by land and river routes. If using the river route, the journey can be done by pompong or speedboat, while the land route can only be traversed by foot, bicycle, or motorbike. This can be seen on the map of Siberut Island, Mentawai Islands Regency.

Figure 1. Map of Siberut Island (Source: Internet)

In this village there is one Elementary School that serves education for local children, which is part of an effort to improve the quality of education in the area. Matotonan Village is not only rich in natural and cultural potential, but also has a community that is committed to preserving local traditions and values. Various traditions are always carried out in Matotonan Village, one of which is Liat Pullagajjat. Liat Pullagajjat is an oral tradition that is rich in cultural and moral values, which is passed down from generation to generation in Matotonan Village, South Siberut. This tradition includes various forms of expression, such as stories, songs, and performances that describe community life, norms, and values that are upheld. Through Liat Pullagajjat, the younger generation is taught about the importance of cooperation, respect, and responsibility for the environment and others.

Liat Pullagajjat Tradition

The Liat Pullagajjat tradition is a village cleaning tradition carried out by Sikerei or clever people (people who lead the ritual) who go looking for leaves to start the Ritual. Then the leaves are placed near the gong after reciting mantras called bakkat kacaila. This Bakkat kacaila is a mystical place led by a Sikebbukat uma called Sibakkat kacaila. This Sibakkat kacaila becomes the leader of every ritual carried out in his tribe called liat (a party, this does not have to be from sikerei, the most important thing is to understand the customs and understand the procession of lia and the oldest in their tribe. One of the oral sentences in the liat pullagajjat ritual is as follows;

Pasibelek

"Kap sikebbukat, ita sipumone kainek, anek kakap saile mui sakit simagre mai sateteu nu si pu lia Anai kuma'nak, kona kona guru'guruk"

Translation:

"Oh you our ancestors, here is an offering to pay for our spirits, your grandchildren who carry out the lia, come, come."

The sentence above is an excerpt of a sentence uttered by Sikerei when performing the pasibelek ritual. The pasibelek ritual is one of the rituals in Lia pulaggajjat. This mantra means to express the release of negative auras that will envelop the celebration of the big village party, a big party held in every village that will hold a village party. Liat pulaggajjat is a big village party that has a very long ritual procession for 3 days and 3 nights. This liat pulaggajjat ritual consists of: Lia Siboitok (taddat lia) Is a small party or the beginning of the party, marked by the beating of tuddukat, gong and gajeumak, The beating is a sign that the party has started, this is done in the early hours of the morning at around 04.00 WIB. Around 7.30 am after doing bele' bubug uma (exchanging part of the roof of the house).

Figure 1. Sikerei Mantra Ritual in Liat Pullagajjat in the Bakkatkacaila Procession
(Source: Zulfa Documentation)

Next, Sikebbukat sibakkat kacaila makes Irig by reciting a ritual on a chicken and anau leaves "Sailaku saila saila ngangan bolo, saila ngangan besi' saila oringen saila simalauru" they believe that through these leaves the anau is free from all anger, danger and disaster when carrying out its work, while a chicken through the sentence sibakkat kacaila (Father of the House) conveys a message of safety with the sentence "Ekeu kina gou"

gou' kut salounu simaeru' areu akek' bolo areu akek besi" You chicken, keep us away from disease and also keep us away from anger, danger, everything we do we will see in your kalang". Next, the chicken's neck is broken and its gallbladder is dissected, they see the salou (good or bad sign) and the anau leaves are distributed to all the invited guests and the community who attended the party, siri muri/Sibakkat katcaila's assistant makes oil to be rubbed on the party participants who attend.

After that they cut pigs and chickens, this food is called Punu Laitak. During this traditional procession, eating and drinking are not allowed from morning to noon and also no sexual intercourse during the party. Furthermore, after they have lunch, some of them get ready to go to the forest to collect leaves to be used at night which is called Pasibitbit Sipitto'.

Next, Pasibitbit (Sipitto') is to expel evil spirits, by taking selected leaves at 4 pm in the forest. At night, summoning spirits as a Sikerei belief where this Sikerei has a spirituality that believes in the help of ancestral spirits and other genies. while the term "Sipitto' is interpreted as an evil spirit that interferes with their activities and their village so that in the afternoon they Sikerei Forestry take materials that are used as a tool to expel Sipitto' at night. After that, the results of the Sipitto' Hunt carried out by the Sikerei were collected and a mantra was read and the closing was sent away with the Sikerei holding leaves walking towards the terrace of the house with the mantra "tuitui-tuitui" Go home-go home.

After all the series of ritual events sikerei and wife continued with the ritual: Lia Sikarua Is the 2nd day party, starting early morning giving a sign to beat tuddukat, gajeuma' and gong like the first lia. Then continued with Pasosok (lia Kasorat) Parade, All Lia participants are ready to wear attributes both Sikerei Sinanalep (Women) or Simatteu (men) as well as simatak (non Sikerei) and other families. In the morning around 08.00 WIB the Liat Pulaggajat Leader gives a sign to turn on the Gong that all participants of this traditional party leave the room before entering the second party. Where sibakkat katcaila assisted by sirimuri makes so'sok or bath water so that all participants are free from disturbances during the traditional procession. After that told to enter the room.

Figure 2. Sinanalep Parade with Writers
(Source: Zulfa Documentation)

Next Iriq toitet Iriq toitet is a series of Lia where iriq is taken from coconut material by reciting a mantra followed by the sound of gajeuma' tokkui and gong then the coconut is opened and eaten after that the sibakkat katcaila gives anau leaves to be attached to the pundangan and participants of the Lia/Party. After that Sibakkat katcaila reads a mantra to the chicken including Sikerei to him and to the other participants with the sentence, Lia ku kina gou'gou' areu ake' bolo, oringen, areu ake' singu, areu ake' sikatai', (O chicken, our illnesses are far away, evil and other disasters in our Village are far away) once finished the chicken's neck is broken and burned after being burned, look at its gallbladder to see if it is a good sign or not.

Figure 3. Orality of Sikerei (Source: Buyamin Documentation)

Then continued with Paeruk Sainak, an activity before slaughtering a pig, the Sikerei read a mantra together in front of the pig while holding Bobblo leaves and a young coconut called Paeru' Sainak, the meaning is that the pig to be slaughtered is a living animal created by Ulau Manua so they believe they must ask permission from God and the spirits before the slaughter is carried out so that later it will be a blessing to those who eat it and a blessing to the owner of the pig. Likewise, they believe that when they raise pigs there will be no disturbance and they can reproduce.

After the Sainak uraji is carried out, it is slaughtered and not immediately burned but hung on the porch poles (Uma) on the left and right. The meaning is so that the pigs that are kept do not immediately disappear from their descendants. What they eat on the second day is called punulaitak from silakra and fish. While the Sikerei eat together facing husband and wife.

Continued with the Pasibelek and Pasialak simagre procession. It is an afternoon activity of the Sikerei Cemetery to call the spirit or soul of the living family called Simagre (Spirit of the Living) it is feared that the simagre is inferior or follows the deceased family so they believe this can be picked up again and persuaded to return to their homes. As for what is left behind are some leaves plus gojo which is given turmeric and planted in the ground, there is also a chicken killed and to be taken home as a tool for the term simagre. This procession can only be done by Sikerei Because when they are crowned their inner eyes are opened to see the Ghoib like Simagre, After returning the chicken is read a mantra and eaten by those who live in the uma with the sentence Doroikap Simagretta. I followed Sikerei to the river near the cemetery near the location.

Figure 4. Pasibelek Ritual (Source: Buyamin Documentation)

Lajot Simagre the next ritual is carried out at night after Simagre is picked up from the grave, starting from soft singing by putting cloths on the terrace of the house and leaves on the tip of the bamboo where it is certain that Simagre does not feel like running away to come to uma so that it is termed the same as parents coaxing their children who have just run away from their home. That night Sikerei performs turuk with fast rotation and while holding a small plate and Jejeneng with a mantra so that until finished it is closed by going around the entire Sikerei holding a bamboo at the end filled with leaves with a mantra that it is considered that the Simagre has been considered gathered until the Sikerei is possessed. After that, singing together and placing a small plate on the head of the Lia participant while reading a mantra then the chicken liver that was dissected when it was buried which was placed on the plate was handed over and eaten by the Lia participant with the assumption that it was Simagre.

Figure 5. Simagre and Lajot Siagre (Source: Buyamin Documentation)

On the third day of Lia Sikatelu, namely the third day of the traditional party, it begins early in the morning by ringing the gong and gajeuma'. Starting from sikebbukat uma (sibakkat katcaila and sirimuri and one Sikerei), they read a mantra to the anau leaves in the hope of being freed from evil and given safety to strive and work before giving them to the party participants.

Figure 6. Iriq (Source: Buyamin Documentation)

Continued on iriq, a series of events of the traditional party where all family members who are participants of the traditional party are counted, so that all of them get a share. After the inauguration ceremony, it is continued with Uraji sainak, which is the reading of a mantra over the slaughtered pork where the spirits of the ancestors are called in the uma to get a share of the meat, hoping that the meat eaten will be blessed and have social value so that the elders can feel their spirits inwardly, this is only Sikerei who feel their arrival apart from Sikerei their descendants, some of whom feel it.

Figure 7. Uraji Sainak (Source: Buyamin Documentation)

This distribution must be equal and no one should be deprived of their rights, because they believe that if that happens there will be a disease for them called Sikaoinan. This is a belief passed down from generation to generation. Then Pukalaibok is a series of events where the Sikerei eat together with their wives facing each other. After that, at dusk, all the invited guests disperse and at midnight, the sikebbukat uma eats katengan uma to prepare for the afternoon parak to the hunting gung. After the evening ceremony, the procession of all the village traditional party events ends. The morning is closed by going hunting for pigs together with the Sikerei who follow the procession of the village traditional party. That is a series of liat pullagajat which is full of all the philosophies of the Mentawai people's lives. There are character education values in this Liat Pullagajat which are present in the community. This is what is starting to disappear in the Mentawai community in general, maintaining the balance of the universe and its creator. If the liat pullagajat ritual is lost, then wait for the destruction of the traditions and culture of the Mentawai people. However, if this is able to maintain as part of the spirit of life of the Mentawai people, the balance of nature will be

maintained forever. The results of the study showed several key findings related to the role of Liat Pullagajjat in strengthening the character of generation 5.0:

1. Character Education: Liat Pullagajjat functions as an effective educational medium, teaching moral and ethical values to the younger generation.
2. Cultural Identity: This tradition helps the younger generation understand and appreciate their cultural identity, which is important in facing the challenges of globalization.
3. Social Skills: Activities involving Liat Pullagajjat improve communication and collaboration skills among the younger generation.
4. Technology Adaptation: The younger generation is taught to integrate this tradition with modern technology, such as social media, to reach a wider audience.

Liat Pullagajjat in Matotonan Village, South Siberut, has an important role in strengthening the character of generation 5.0. Through character education, strengthening cultural identity, and improving social skills, this tradition contributes to the formation of a younger generation that is not only technologically intelligent, but also rich in cultural and moral values. Therefore, the preservation of Liat Pullagajjat must continue to be encouraged through collaboration between traditional leaders, educators, and the community.

CONCLUSION

Liat Pullagajjat in Matotonan Village, South Siberut, is not only an oral tradition, but also an effective tool in strengthening the character of generation 5.0. Through character education, strengthening cultural identity, and improving social skills, and adapting to technology. Liat Pullagajjat contributes to the formation of a better young generation. Therefore, it is important to preserve and promote Liat Pullagajjat as part of character development efforts in the digital era. The ritual process in carrying out the Liat Pullagajjat tradition begins with Lia Siboitok (taddat lia), Sikebbukat sibakkat katcaila, Pasibitbit Sipitto', Lia Sikarua, Iriq toitet Iriq toitet, Lajot Simagre, Lia Sikatelu, Uraji sainak, and Pukalaibok. This ritual is guided by all sikerei in Matotonan, Madobag and Butui villages located in the South Siberut sub-district of the Mentawai Islands Regency. Liat Pullagajjat tradition as a cultural heritage of the ancestors of the Mentawai people which is a reflection of the extinct Arat Sabulungan. For the Indonesian nation which must be maintained and preserved.

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